

FUNCTIONAL SPACES . IN SHORT REFLECTION PRINCIPLE

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ANNOTATION.

In the article local boundary and nonlocal problems for classical equations of mathematical physics are better studied using classical methods. These problems are studied in the theory of generalized functions by modern (functional) methods in Sobolev spaces, the principle of reduced reflection .

Key words : Lebesgue space , Sobolev space , metric space , normalized space

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In the article, the local boundary and non-local problems for classical equations of mathematical physics are better studied using classical methods. In the theory of generalized functions, these problems are studied by modern (functional) methods in Sobolev spaces, the principle of reduced reflection.

Key words: Lebesgue space, Sobolev space , metric space, normalized space L1[a,b]. Here, L1[a,b]the elements of the normed space [a,b]are continuous functions defined on the interval, where is x(t)the norm of the function

||x(t)|| = integral from a to b of |x(t)| dt

equality through determined will be _

[a,b]in between determined {xn(t)} and {xn*(t)} continuously functions sequences given let it be If{xn(t) - xn*(t)} succession _ _ L1[a,b] normalized in space infinite small if , that is n -> infinity at

||xn(t) - xn*(t)|| = integral from a to b of |xn(t) - xn*(t)| dt -> 0

if , then {xn(t)} and {xn*(t)} continuously functions sequences L1[a,b]normalized in space equivalent or average in a sense is said to be equivalent .

If optional epsilon > 0 for a positive number so one N = N(epsilon) no there is is optional _ n >= N for and optional p in N natural number for

||xn+p - xn|| = integral from a to b of |xn+p(t) - xn(t)| dt < epsilon ,

inequality appropriate if , then [a,b]in between determined {x_n(t)} and {x_n^*(t)} continuously functions sequences are fundamental or average it is said to be fundamental in the meaning .

Filling about to the theorem basically L[a,b] Lebesgue space average in a sense equivalent and average was fundamental in meaning continuously functions of succession _ from the class consists of has been x-hat of the elements Created will be

Average was fundamental in meaning [a,b]in between determined {x_n(t)} continuously functions sequences one x-hat(t) from class to be for their average in a sense equivalent to be necessary and is enough . If{x_n(t)} in x-hat(t) if , then _ definition according to

||x-hat||_{L[a,b]} = lim_{n to inf} integral_a^b |x_n(t)| dt = lim_{n to inf} ||x_n(t)||_{L_1[a,b]} (1.3.1)

equality with is determined .

From this except (1) expression |x-hat(t)| from the function received Lebesgue we call it an integral , in which x-hat(t) in L[a,b] will be _ To the description according to expression (1.3.1).

integral_a^b |x-hat(t)| dt = lim_{n to inf} integral_a^b |x_n(t)| dt

in the form of is the left - hand side Lebesgue integral , right on the side while Riemann is integral .

L_p(G), p >= 1 Lebesgue space _ Previous in point considered space a little more general was _ become transfer let's look .G set _ R^n in space limited field let it be G-bar while that's it G of the field closed i let it be L_p(G), p >= 1 Lebesgue space L_p(G-bar), p >= 1 linear normalized of space filler _ as is determined .

L_p(G), p >= 1 Lebesgue of space elements L[a,b] Lebesgue as in space as some " functions " . to him G-bar closed in the field determined continuously functions with average approach in the sense of desired in accuracy zoom in possible will L_p(G-bar), p >= 1 be linear normalized space L_p(G), p >= 1 Lebesgue in space dense will be

If n,m to inf G-bar closed in the collection determined {u_n(x)} continuously functions sequence _ _ for

||u_n - u_m||_{L_p(G-bar)}^p = integral_G |u_n(x) - u_m(x)|^p dx -> 0

if , then $\bar{G}$ closed in the collection determined $\{u_n(x)\}$ continuously functions sequence $_{-} L_p(\bar{G}), p \geq 1$ linear normalized fundamental in space or P – level average it is said to be fundamental in the meaning .

If $\{u_n(x) - u_n^*(x)\}$ succession $_{-} L_p(\bar{G}), p \geq 1$ normalized in space infinite small if , that is, in $n \rightarrow \infty$

$$\|u_n(x) - u_n^*(x)\|_{L_p(\bar{G})}^p = \int_G |u_n(x) - u_n^*(x)|^p dx \rightarrow 0$$

if , then $\{u_n(x)\}$ and $\{u_n^*(x)\}$ continuously functions sequences $_{-} L_p(\bar{G}), p \geq 1$ normalized in space equivalent or p –level average in a sense is said to be equivalent . It's both even $\bar{G}$ without closed set $_{-}$ according to received n – times Riemann integral mean caught $_{-}$

Sobolev space

General definition $_{-} R^m$ in space $\bar{G}$ closed limited field given let it be That's it $\bar{G}$ closed limited in the field l times continuously differentiable $u: \bar{G} \rightarrow R^1$ (simplicity for real value) was $_{-} u(x)$ of functions linear space let's look $\bar{G}$ closed limited in the field Differentiability is different in a sense to understand can $_{-}$ We are $u(x)$ a function G in the field l times continuously differentiable and each $_{-}$ private derivative G from the field received x that's the point G of the field at the border optional to the point when striving finite to the limit have We think that it will be . As a result every one of them private of the derivative $\bar{G}$ to the field continuation that's it $\bar{G}$ closed limited in the field continuously was $_{-}$ from the function consists of will be This is us on the ground G of the field Γ the limit enough we consider smooth . From this except , usually G field one the garden is lame and another addition conditions satisfaction some we require in cases . This is under review linear in space the norm concept $p \geq 1$ for

$\|u\| = \left\{ \int_G |u(x)|^p dx + \sum_{1 \leq |a| \leq l} \int_G |D^a u(x)|^p dx \right\}$ we introduce with equality. We denote by the

normed space formed by which all axioms of the norm are reasonable, $W_p^l(\bar{G})$ and it is called the Sobolev space.

In short reflection principle

Let's assume X metric in the space of , that's it of space the elements of this space to the elements planter A , operator is given let it be From this except X of space optional x and y elements for , the following inequality appropriate let it be $\rho(A(x), A(y)) \leq \alpha \rho(x, y)$, this on the ground $\alpha < 1$. In that case X in space such a single point x_0 , there is it will be his for $A(x_0) = x_0$, equality

appropriate will be Here $\rho(x, y)$ – through X space optional elements x and y between the distance let's define .

Definition 1.1.2. [108],[126] Operator A, B in space shortening reflective ρ called , if the following conditions if done :

1) $\phi \in B$, if then $A\phi \in B$, that is $A: B \rightarrow B$;

2) B of space optional ϕ_1, ϕ_2 – elements for ρ , the following inequalities appropriate if $\|A\phi_1 - A\phi_2\|_B \leq \rho \|\phi_1 - \phi_2\|_B$, this on the ground $\rho < 1$.

Theorem 1.1.1. (Banach) [108], [126]. Full metric in space optional shortening reflection is the only immovable to the point z will be

Theorem 1.1.2. (compactness about .) [120], [126].

Let's assume B – banah space be , $\{x_n\}$ - this in space limited sequence be , then this $\{x_n\}$ from the sequence $x \in B$ to the point weak approaching partial sequence $\{x_{n_j}\}$ separate possible and his for the following inequality appropriate .

$$\|x\| \leq \lim_{n_j \rightarrow \infty} \|x_{n_j}\| \leq \overline{\lim_{n_j \rightarrow \infty} \|x_{n_j}\|}.$$

Theorem 1.1.3. If optional $\varphi(x) \in L_2(\Omega)$ for , the following equality appropriate if $\int_{\Omega} g(x)\varphi(x)dx = 0$, in that case $g(x) = 0$ equality $L_2(\Omega)$ of space almost

everyone in place appropriate will be [120], [171].

natural science create the need to formulate and study qualitatively new problems, as a vivid example of which is the research of non-linear boundary problems .

The relations connecting the value of the solution and its derivatives at the boundary and interior points of the field are called nonlocal problems. In the theory of nonlocal boundary value problems for differential equations, there are many open and understudied problems of both theoretical and practical interest that need to be addressed. Among them, for example, we note a wide category of questions related to the uniqueness, existence and stability (stationarity) of solutions.

AV Bitsadze and AA Samarsky were the first to propose and study these problems for elliptic equations. Later these problems were called Bitsadze-Samarsky problems. In recent decades, nonlocal problems for differential equations have been actively studied by many mathematicians. To date, local

boundary and nonlocal problems for classical equations of mathematical physics have been well studied using classical methods. But these issues are not well studied in Sobolev spaces by modern (functional) methods in the theory of generalized functions.

This determines the relevance of our article .

References:

1. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). CAPUTA MA'NOSIDA KASR TARTIBLI HOSILALAR VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 360-365.
2. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). MAXSUS SOHALARDA KARLEMAN MATRITSASI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 137-141.
3. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). APPROXIMATION OF FUNCTIONS WITH COEFFICIENTS. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 135–138.
4. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). Applications of the double integral to mechanical problems. International journal of sciearchers, 2(2), 101-103.
5. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). FINDING THE MAXIMUM AND MINIMUM VALUE OF A FUNCTION ON A SEGMENT. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 245-248.
6. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). FUNKSIYALARNI KOEFFITSIENTLAR ORQALI FUNKSIYALARNI YAKINLASHTIRISH HAQIDA MA'LUMOTLAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 102–110.
7. Sharipova, M. (2023, December). RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN STRAIGHT LINES AND PLANES IN SPACE. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 2, No. 12, pp. 60-66).
8. Sharipova, M. (2023). FRACTIONAL DERIVATIVES. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(27), 106-113.
9. Sharipova, M. (2023). CORRECT PLACED AND CORRECT NOT PLACED ISSUES. Models and methods in modern science, 2(13), 115-121.
10. Sharipova, M. (2023). HEAT SPREAD EQUATION. Инновационные исследования в науке, 2(12), 50-56.
11. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). HIGH MATH SCORE AND INTERVAL ASSESSMENT. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 420–424.
12. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). IN HIGHER MATHEMATICS, THE EXTREMUM OF A MULTIVARIABLE FUNCTION. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 425–429.

13. Sharipova, M. P. (2024). ISSIQLIK TARQALISH TENGLAMASI UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 525-532.
14. Axmedova, Z. I. (2023). LMS TIZIMIDA INTERAKTIV ELEMENTLARNI YARATISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 368-372.
15. Axmedova, Z. (2023). MOODLE TIZIMI VA UNING IMKONIYATLARI. Development and innovations in science, 2(11), 29-35.
16. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). USING THE USEFUL ASPECTS OF THE MOODLE SYSTEM AND ITS POSSIBILITIES. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 201-205.
17. Zulxumor, A. (2022). IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERACTIVE COURSES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. ILMIY TADQIQOT VA INNOVATSIYA, 1(6), 128-132.
18. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). SQL (STRUCTURED QUERY LANGUAGE) STATISTICAL PACKAGES OF CAPABILITIES. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 2(12), 781-787.
19. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). SQL (STRUCTURED QUERY LANGUAGE) CAPABILITIES OF THE STATISTICAL DATABASE LANGUAGE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 274-280.
20. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). CREATION AND PLACEMENT OF INTERACTIVE ELEMENTS. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 2(13), 120-128.
21. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS, ELECTRONIC EDUCATION: TASKS AND OPPORTUNITIES. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(21), 171-177.
22. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). DISADVANTAGES OF ELECTRONIC LEARNING. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 2(12), 99-109.
23. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). SQL SPECIFICATIONS FOR DATA ANALYSIS. Science and innovation in the education system, 2(13), 113-120.
24. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). Programming Environments for Creating Mobile Applications on the Android Operating System. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 305-309.
25. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). CAPUTO MA'NOSIDAGI KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO'YICHA TO'G'RI MASALALAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 375-382.
26. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). BETA FUNKSIYA XOSSALARI VA BU FUNKSIYA YORDAMIDA TURLI MASALALARNI YECHISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 66-76.

27. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). KASR TARTIBLI ODDIY DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 383–390.
28. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). GAMMA FUNKSIYA. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 391–399.
29. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
30. Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal, 1(10), 13-23.
31. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). HEAT PHYSICAL MEANING AND ORIGIN OF DIFFUSION EQUATIONS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
32. daughter Latipova, S. S. (2023). HEAT PHYSICAL MEANING AND ORIGIN OF DIFFUSION EQUATIONS. World of Scientific news in Science, 1(2), 163-176.
33. Shahnoza, L. (2023, March). KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA VA BOSHLANG'ICH FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO'YICHA TESKARI MASALALAR. In " Conference on Universal Science Research 2023" (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 8-10).
34. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). RIMAN-LUIVILL KASR TARTIBLI INTEGRALI VA HOSILASIGA OID AYRIM MASALALARNING ISHLANISHI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(12), 216-220.
35. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). MITTAG–LIFFLER FUNKSIYASI VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 238-244.
36. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). KASR TARTIBLI HOSILA TUSHUNCHASI. SCHOLAR, 1(31), 263-269.
37. Bobokulova, M. X. (2023). STOMATOLOGIK MATERIALLARNING FIZIK-MEXANIK XOSSALARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 223-228.
38. Xamroyevna, B. M. (2023). ORGANIZM TO 'QIMALARINING ZICHLIGINI ANIQLASH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 50-58.
39. Khamroyevna, M. B. (2023). PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF BIOLOGICAL MEMBRANES, BIOPHYSICAL MECHANISMS OF MOVEMENT OF SUBSTANCES IN THE MEMBRANE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 217-221.
40. Bobokulova, M. K. (2023). IMPORTANCE OF FIBER OPTIC DEVICES IN MEDICINE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 212-216.

41. Mukhtaram Bobokulova Khamroyevna. (2023). Radiation Protection. Dosimetry . Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 4(6), 134-139.
42. Bobokulova, M. K. (2024). TOLALI OPTIKA ASBOBLARINING TIBBIYOTDAGI AHAMIYATI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 517-524.
43. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). Zamonaviy ta'limda axborot texnologiyalari va ularni qo'llash usul va vositalari. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 481-486.
44. Муродов, О. Т. (2023). РАЗРАБОТКА АВТОМАТИЗИРОВАННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ И ВЛАЖНОСТИ В ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫХ КОМНАТ. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(26), 91-95.
45. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISHDA INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(32), 194-201.
46. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA FANINI O'QITISHDA YANGI INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH METODIKASI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 130-139.
47. MURODOV, O. T. (2023). INNOVATIVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND NEW METHODS AND TOOLS FOR THEIR APPLICATION IN TODAY'S EDUCATION. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
48. Turakulovich, M. O. (2023). DEVELOPMENT AND INSTALLATION OF AN AUTOMATIC TEMPERATURE CONTROL SYSTEM IN ROOMS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
49. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. li.(2023). Mobil ilovalar yaratish va ularni bajarish jarayoni. International journal of scientific researchers, 2(2).
50. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. (2023). USE OF ARTIFICIAL NERVOUS SYSTEMS IN MODELING. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 269-273.
51. Behruz Ulugbek og, Q. (2023). TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE: A DYNAMIC PARTNERSHIP. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(11).
52. Quvvatov, B. U. o'g'li . (2023). ALEXNET - TASVIRLARNI TASNIFLASH UCHUN KONVOLYUTSION NEYRON TARMOQ. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 77-90.
53. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g'li Quvvatov. (2023). MAXIMUM PRINCIPLE AND ERROR ANALYSIS. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 480-486.
54. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). RSA VA EL-GAMAL OCHIQ KALITLI SHIFRLASH ALGORITMI ASOSIDA ELEKTRON RAQMLI IMZOLARI. RSA OCHIQ

KALITLI SHIFRLASH ALGORITMI ASOSIDAGI ELEKTRON RAQAMLI IMZO. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 316-319.

55. Sharopova, M. M. qizi . (2023). JAVA TILI YORDAMIDA OB'EKTGA YUNALTIRILGAN DASTURLASH ASOSLARI BILAN TANISHISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 111-119.

56. Sharopova, M. (2023). CHOOSE: COMPOSITION OR INHERITANCE. Science and innovation in the education system, 2(13), 96-102.

57. Sharopova, M. (2023). JAVA PROGRAMMING IN THE LANGUAGE HERITAGE TO DO SYNTAX. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 2(12), 82-87.

58. Sharopova, M. (2023). ARRAY AND ARRAYS INSTALLATION. Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 2(12), 102-107.

59. Sharopova, M. (2023). CLASSES AGAIN APPLY. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 2(13), 106-111.

60. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). INTRODUCING" PROGRAM CONTROL OPERATORS" IN THE JAVA PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 222-231.

61. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). Working with folders in the JAVA programming language. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 232-236.

62. Sharopova, M. (2024). DSA ERI STANDARD. ELECTRONIC DIGITAL SIGNATURE OF GOST R 34.10-94. B THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES (T. 3, Выпуск 1, cc. 169-178).

63. Sharopova, M. (2024). ELECTRONIC DIGITAL SIGNATURE ALGORITHMS BASED ON THE COMPLEXITY OF THE FACTORIZATION PROBLEM. B SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM (T. 3, Выпуск 1, cc. 66-74).

64. Sharopova, M. (2024). ARRAYS AND ARRAYS INSTALLATION. B CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES (T. 3, Выпуск 1, cc. 102-110).

65. Sharopova, M. (2024). JAVA PROGRAMMING IN THE LANGUAGE FLOWING INPUT AND RELEASE. B SOLUTION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN MANAGEMENT AND ECONOMY (T. 3, Выпуск 1, cc. 84-93).

66. Sharopova, M. (2024). COLLECTORS. (OBJECT CONTAINERS). B DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN SCIENCES (T. 3, Выпуск 1, cc. 93-101).

67. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED SYSTEM FOR CONTROLLING TEMPERATURE AND HUMIDITY IN PRODUCTION ROOMS. В DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATIONS IN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 84–93).
68. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED PARAMETER CONTROL SYSTEM ROOMS AND WORKSHOPS BASED ON CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES. В ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 2, сс. 16–27).
69. Muradov, O. (2024). BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. В MODELS AND METHODS IN MODERN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 84–93).
70. Muradov, O. (2024). APPLIED TO THE CURRENT TRAINING PROCESS REQUIREMENTS. В INNOVATIVE RESEARCH IN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 54–63).
71. Muradov, O. (2024). APPLICATION OF BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES TO EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES. В МЕЖДУРОДНАЯ КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ АКАДЕМИЧЕСКИХ НАУК (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 46–55).
72. Tursunov, B. J., & Allanazarov, G. O. (2019). Perspektivnyye tehnologii proizvodstva po uluchsheniyu kachestva benzina. Theory and practice of contemporary science, 3(45), 305-308.
73. Турсунов, Б. Ж., & Алланазаров, Г. О. (2019). Перспективные технологии производства по улучшению качества бензина. Теория и практика современной науки, (3 (45)), 305-308.
74. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Analysis of Concepts About the Effect of an Explosion in Solid Wednesday. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 296-304.
75. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Methods of Control of Explosion Energy Distribution in Rocks. Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies (2993-2599), 1(10), 108-117.
76. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). WASTE-FREE TECHNOLOGY FOR ENRICHMENT OF PURIFIC COPPER-ZINC ORE. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 288-293.
77. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). ANALYSIS OF MODERN METHODS FOR OIL SLUDGE PROCESSING. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 280-287.
78. Jumaev, K., & Tursunov, B. (2022, December). Environmentally friendly technology for obtaining fuel briquettes from oil waste. In IOP Conference

Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 1112, No. 1, p. 012005). IOP Publishing.

79. Ахмедова, О. Б., Турсунов, Б. Ж., & угли Худойбердиев, Н. Н. (2022). Анализ физико-химических свойств нефтешламов Бухарского НПЗ и рациональные способы их утилизации. Science and Education, 3(6), 495-507.

80. Турсунов, Б. Д. (2016). Анализ и выявление путей совершенствования процессов горного дела. Молодой ученый, (23), 105-106.

81. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). СОЗДАНИЕ ПРОГРАММЫ ДЛЯ ИМИТАЦИИ ШИФРОВАНИЯ МАШИНЫ ENIGMA НА ЯЗЫКЕ PYTHON. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 317-323.

82. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). STUDY THE PSYCHOLOGY OF PROGRAMMERS. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 563-568.

83. Jurakulov, S. Z. O., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). THE MAIN SIGNIFICANCE OF THE DEPARTMENTS OF PHYSICS IN THE DEVELOPMENT. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 162-167.

84. Jurakulov, S. Z. O., & Turdiboyev, H. (2023). RELATIONSHIPS OF PHYSICS WITH ART IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 144-147.

85. Jurakulov, S. Z. O., & Turdiboyev, H. (2023). ADVANCED STRATEGIES FOR LEARNING PHYSICS. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 152-156.

86. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). IN THE EDUCATIONAL FIELD OF PHYSICS LEVEL AND POSITION. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 157-161.

87. Jurakulov, S. (2023). PROPERTIES AND CHARACTERISTICS OF NUCLEAR ENERGY. Инновационные исследования в науке, 2(12), 35-39.

88. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Hamidov, E. (2023). YADRO ENERGIYASINING XOSSA VA XUSUSIYATLARI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 182-186.

89. IN THE EDUCATIONAL FIELD OF PHYSICS LEVEL AND POSITION

90. SZ Jurakulov, O Nurboyev - GOLDEN BRAIN, 2023

91. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Turdiboyev, X. (2023). FIZIKA FANINI O 'RGANISHNING YUQORI DARAJADAGI STRATEGIYALAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 152-156.

92. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Turdiboyev, X. (2023). TA'LIM SOHASIDA FIZIKANING SAN'AT BILAN ALOQALARI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 144-147.

93. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). FIZIKA FANINING BO 'LIMLARINING RIVOJLANISHDAGIDAGI ASOSIY AHAMIYATI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 162-167.

94. Jurakulov, S. (2023). ON THE RELATION OF METAPHYSICS TO PHYSICS. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(27), 9-20.

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96. Jurakulov, S. (2023). IMPACT OF THE MINING INDUSTRY ON PEOPLE AND THE ENVIRONMENT. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(21), 143-150.
97. Jurakulov, S. (2023). CHANGES IN LANGUAGE DUE TO NEW PHYSICS. Models and methods in modern science, 2(13), 77-87.